

How to Deal with Privacy, Bias & Drift in Synthetic Primary Care Data

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IDA
Research

The Talk

- Why we need synthetic data
- Importance of fidelity
- Importance of privacy
- Handling bias
- Handling geolocation
- Handling drift

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Nick Trigg
Health correspondent

19 February 2014

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OUTLOOK | 27 April 2023

Synthetic data could be better than real data

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Synthetic Data Is About To Transform Artificial Intelligence

Rob Toews Contributor

I write about the big picture of artificial intelligence.

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Generative Models in Literature

Goncalves et al. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-020-00977-1>

(2020) 20:108

BMC Medical Research
Methodology

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Open Access

Generation and evaluation of synthetic patient data

Andre Goncalves^{1*}, Priyadip Ray¹, Braden Soper¹, Jennifer Stevens², Linda Coyle² and Ana Paula Sales¹

Abstract

Background: Machine learning (ML) has made a significant impact in medicine and cancer research; however, its impact in these areas has been undeniably slower and more limited than in other application domains. A major reason for this has been the lack of availability of patient data to the broader ML research community, in large part due to patient privacy protection concerns. High-quality, realistic, synthetic datasets can be leveraged to accelerate methodological developments in medicine. By and large, medical data is high dimensional and often categorical. These characteristics pose multiple modeling challenges.

Methods: In this paper, we evaluate three classes of synthetic data generation approaches; probabilistic models, classification-based imputation models, and generative adversarial neural networks. Metrics for evaluating the quality

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Volume 26, Issue 3

March 2019

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Abstract

BACKGROUND AND
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RESULTS

Synthesizing electronic health records using improved generative adversarial networks ^{FREE}

Mrinal Kanti Baowaly ✉, Chia-Ching Lin, Chao-Lin Liu, Kuan-Ta Chen

Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association, Volume 26, Issue 3, March 2019,

Pages 228–241, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocy142>

Published: 07 December 2018 [Article history ▾](#)

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Abstract

Objective

The aim of this study was to generate synthetic electronic health records (EHRs). The generated EHR data will be more realistic than those generated using the existing medical Generative Adversarial Network (medGAN) method.

Materials and Methods

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Generative Models in Literature

Goncalves et al. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-020-00977-1>

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Abstract

Background: Machine learning (ML) has made a significant impact in medicine and cancer research; however, its impact in these areas has been undeniably slower and more limited than in other application domains. A major reason for this has been the lack of availability of patient data to the broader ML research community, in large part due to patient privacy protection concerns. High-quality, realistic, synthetic datasets can be leveraged to accelerate

The results showed that Bayesian Networks, Mixture of Product of Multinomials (MPoM) and CLGP were capable of capturing variables relationships, considering the data utility metrics used for comparison. Surprisingly, the generative adversarial network-based model MC-MedGAN failed to generate data with similar statistical characteristics to the real dataset.

Volume 26, Issue 3

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Article Contents

Abstract

BACKGROUND AND
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RESULTS

Results

We conducted a comprehensive analysis and found our models were adequately efficient for generating synthetic EHR data. The proposed models outperformed medGAN in all cases, and among the 3 models, boundary-seeking GAN (medBGAN) performed the best.

Discussion

To generate realistic synthetic EHR data, the proposed models will be effective in the medical industry and related research from the viewpoint of providing better services. Moreover, they will eliminate barriers including limited access to EHR data and thus accelerate research on medical informatics.

Conclusion

The proposed models can adequately learn the data distribution of real EHRs and efficiently generate realistic synthetic EHRs. The results show the superiority of our models over the existing model.

Generative Models in Literature

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GOGGLE: Generative Modelling for Tabular Data by Learning Relational Structure

Tennison Liu, Zhaozhi Qian, Jeroen Berrevoets, Mihaela van der Schaar

Published: 01 Feb 2023, Last Modified: 01 Mar 2023 ICLR 2023 poster Readers: Everyone Show Bibtex Show Revisions

Keywords: tabular data, synthetic data, generative model

Abstract: Deep generative models learn highly complex and non-linear representations to generate realistic synthetic data. While they have achieved notable success in computer vision and natural language processing, similar advances have been less demonstrable in the tabular domain. This is partially because generative modelling of tabular data entails a particular set of challenges, including heterogeneous relationships, limited number of samples, and difficulties in incorporating prior knowledge. Additionally, unlike their counterparts in image and sequence domain, deep generative models for tabular data almost exclusively employ fully-connected layers, which encode weak inductive biases about relationships between inputs. Real-world data generating processes can often be represented using relational structures, which encode sparse, heterogeneous relationships between variables. In this work, we learn and exploit relational structure underlying tabular data to better model variable dependence, and as a natural means to introduce regularization on relationships and include prior knowledge. Specifically, we introduce GOGGLE, an end-to-end message passing scheme that jointly learns the relational structure and corresponding functional relationships as the basis of generating synthetic samples. Using real-world datasets, we provide empirical evidence that the proposed method is effective in generating realistic synthetic data and exploiting domain knowledge for downstream tasks.

Anonymous Url: I certify that there is no URL (e.g., github page) that could be used to find authors' identity.

No Acknowledgement Section: I certify that there is no acknowledgement section in this submission for double blind review.

Supplementary Material: zip

Code Of Ethics: I acknowledge that I and all co-authors of this work have read and commit to adhering to the ICLR Code of Ethics

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DECAF: Generating Fair Synthetic Data Using Causally-Aware Generative Networks

Part of [Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 34 \(NeurIPS 2021\)](#)

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Authors

Boris van Breugel, Trent Kyono, Jeroen Berrevoets, Mihaela van der Schaar

Abstract

Machine learning models have been criticized for reflecting unfair biases in the training data. Instead of solving for this by introducing fair learning algorithms directly, we focus on generating fair synthetic data, such that any downstream learner is fair. Generating fair synthetic data from unfair data - while remaining truthful to the underlying data-generating process (DGP) - is non-trivial. In this paper, we introduce DECAF: a GAN-based fair synthetic data generator for tabular data. With DECAF we embed the DGP explicitly as a structural causal model in the input layers of the generator, allowing each variable to be reconstructed conditioned on its causal parents. This procedure enables inference time debiasing, where biased edges can be strategically removed for satisfying user-defined fairness requirements. The DECAF framework is versatile and compatible with several popular definitions of fairness. In our experiments, we show that DECAF

Probabilistic Graphical Networks

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Article | Open Access | Published: 09 November 2020

Generating high-fidelity synthetic patient data for assessing machine learning healthcare software

Allan Tucker, Zhenchen Wang, Ylenia Rotalinti & Puja Myles

npj Digital Medicine 3, Article number: 147 (2020) | Cite this article

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FCI algorithm

- FCI algorithm (Spirtes et al. 2001) is able to determine existence of latent confounders.
 - (A) Original true causal graph.
 - (B) After edges are removed because of conditional independence relations.
 - (C) The output of FCI, indicating that there is at least one unmeasured confounder of Y and Z.
- Better fit to data?

Probabilistic Graphical Networks

Latent Variables
Incorporated into
Model of
Primary Care Data

Fidelity

Fidelity – CPRD

ground truth

synthetic data

	a) Ground Truth – including missing data		b) Synthetic Data - Modelling GT in a) with missing nodes		c) Synthetic Data - Modelling GT in a) with latent variables	
Factor	Distinct / Missing	Distribution	Distinct / Missing	Distribution	Distinct / Missing	Distribution
age	84 / 0		84 / 0		84 / 0	
strokeha	2 / 0	F:93.6% T:6.4%	2 / 0	F:93.8% T:6.2%	2 / 0	F:93.6% T:6.4%
bmi	580 / 15.73		437 / 7.08		437 / 0.01	
choleratio	573 / 88.59		80 / 41.93		80 / 0.08	
smoking	5 / 0	1: (76.7%) 1: (14.2%) 2: (3.4%) 3: (3.9%) 4: (1.8%)	5 / 0	1: (76.8%) 1: (14.1%) 2: (3.3%) 3: (4.0%) 4: (1.8%)	5 / 0	1: (76.8%) 1: (14.1%) 2: (3.3%) 3: (4.0%) 4: (1.8%)

Time-Series Fidelity – MIMIC

a Two independent autoregressions

b Aligned at maximum cross correlation

Time-Series Fidelity – MIMIC

Fidelity – Health Tech / CPRD

Iteration	ROC & PR curves (P=Positive cases, N = Negative cases)	Granger causality p value ($\alpha=0.05$): PR, ROC	AUC GT: PR, ROC	AUC SYN: PR, ROC
1		<0.001, <0.001	0.293, 0.812	0.346, 0.881
2		<0.001, <0.001	0.292, 0.818	0.341, 0.881
3		<0.001, <0.001	0.274, 0.797	0.349, 0.880

Synthetic Data & Privacy

Simulating attack - Matching to Real Patients

Distance threshold

3 Synthetic NN are close to the GT patient A and 2 Synthetic patients are close to GT patient B within the distance radius.

GT Attributes	Num Of GT Outliers	Num Of GT Patients in 10000 Sample	Num of Single Synth NN	Proportion of GT Outliers with Single Synth NN
age, smoking, region, gender, ethnicity, ckidney	396.3	6248	113.8	1.82%
age, smoking, region, gender, ethnicity, bmi, sbps, ckidney	377	6250	77.7	1.24%
age, smoking, region, gender, ethnicity, bmi, choleraio, sbp, sbps, ckidney	363.1	6289	48.22	0.76%
age, smoking, region, gender, ethnicity, bmi, sbps, ckidney, sle, atyantip, type1, steroid	363.4	6180	43.5	0.70%

Example output:

Press release

New synthetic datasets to assist COVID-19 and cardiovascular research

Ground-breaking innovation to support medical technologies

Published 29 July 2020

From: [Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency](#)

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Synthetic data

CPRD has generated a number of synthetic datasets that can be used for training purposes or to improve algorithms or machine learning workflows.

Two high-fidelity synthetic datasets are being made available with a nominal administrative fee:

- [CPRD cardiovascular disease synthetic dataset](#)
- [CPRD COVID-19 symptoms and risk factors synthetic dataset](#)

An additional fee will apply for an annual teaching licence for the high-fidelity synthetic datasets.

CPRD has also developed sample datasets for CPRD GOLD and CPRD Aurum, medium-fidelity synthetic datasets that resemble the real world CPRD primary care databases.

- [CPRD Aurum and CPRD GOLD sample datasets](#)

Find out about [pricing information on our web page](#) or by contacting enquiries@cprd.com.

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Synthetic Data & Privacy

- K-anonymisation: removing or generalising data
 - but what is an acceptable K?
 - not good on high dimensions
- Differential Privacy: removing an individual has no effect on analysis
 - but repeated requests for aggregate data enabling id of individuals
 - Impact of rare cases (elderly individuals / rare disease / personalised medicine)

Simulating attack – Adversarial Suite - TAPAS

“Privacy is not actually that well understood. Scientists can assign a numerical value to the privacy level of a data set, but we don’t exactly know which values should be considered safe or not.”, Florimund Houssiau, Alan Turing Institute

Synthetic Data & Bias

Sampling Bias and Prejudice in AI

THE LANCET

COMMENT | VOLUME 397, ISSUE 10286, P1684-1685, MAY 08, 2021

COVID-19 and disparities affecting ethnic minorities

Daniel R Morales Sarah N Ali

Published: April 30, 2021 • DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(21\)00949-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(21)00949-1) Check for updates

Two Petty Theft Arrests

Borden was rated high risk for future crime after she and a friend took a kid's bike and scooter that were sitting outside. She did not reoffend.

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Technology

Thousands more back Dr Timnit Gebru over Google 'sacking'

By Cristina Criddle
Technology reporter

8 December 2020

Scientists have expressed support for a leading artificial-intelligence ethics researcher who says Google fired her.

An open letter demanding transparency has now been signed by more than 4,500 people, including DeepMind researchers and UK academics.

Google denies Timnit Gebru's account of events that led to her leaving the company.

Bias & Transparency

- Our models are learnt from huge datasets
- But these datasets can still be biased (secondary data analysis)
- How do we detect these?
- How do we resolve biases in the model?
 - Spurious Correlations
 - Under-sampling
 - Proxies for prejudice
 - Biased labels

Bias & Transparency

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 - **Spurious Correlations**
 - Under-sampling
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 - Biased labels

Transparent Models

Latent Variables
Incorporated into
Model of
Primary Care Data

Bias & Transparency

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- But these datasets can still be biased (secondary data analysis)
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Handling Under-sampling Bias: Boosting

- Boosting Methods

SMOTE (Chawla et al., JAIR 2002) :

- Nearest neighbours for each minority class sample
- Sample synthetic points along these lines

ADASYN adds noise

- ▨ Majority class samples
- Minority class samples
- Synthetic samples

Handling Under-Sampling Bias: BayesBoost

- **BayesBoost**

(Draghi et al., ECML 2021):

Do not simply try to create balanced classes

- a) Identify undersampled cases using uncertainty in prediction
- b) Boost these cases using the Bayesian Network Synthetic Data Generator
- c) Experiment with degree of boosting

- Case study on ethnic groups: Predicting stroke and heart attacks.
- Compare distribution of ethnicity on GT and of uncertain cases
- Boost using the synthetic generator

Classification Accuracy

- Classification accuracy and 95% confidence intervals obtained by testing the datasets of interest in predicting stroke and heart attacks.
- BayesBoost
 - Overcomes ethnicity biases
 - Improves classification accuracy in predicting desired diseases.

Data	Protected Attribute	Target	Dataset	CI low	Classification Accuracy	CI up	AUC ROC	AUC P-R
CVD	Ethnicity	Stroke	D _{Bias}	0.793	0.795	0.796	0.741	0.37
			BB50	0.824	0.826	0.827	0.746	0.37
			BB100	0.827	0.829	0.83	0.74	0.37
			BB200	0.828	0.83	0.831	0.73	0.36
			SMOTE	0.715	0.717	0.718	0.73	0.37
			AdaSyn	0.687	0.688	0.69	0.73	0.37
			Fair-SMOTE	-	0.65	-	0.63	0.4
CVD	Ethnicity	Atrial Fibrillation	D _{Bias}	0.887	0.888	0.889	0.8	0.19
			BB50	0.927	0.928	0.929	0.81	0.18
			BB100	0.934	0.935	0.936	0.81	0.18
			BB200	0.94	0.941	0.942	0.79	0.18
			SMOTE	0.744	0.746	0.748	0.79	0.18
			AdaSyn	0.741	0.742	0.744	0.79	0.18
			Fair-SMOTE	-	0.71	-	0.7	0.4
CVD	Ethnicity	Type 2 Diabetes	D _{Bias}	0.821	0.823	0.824	0.712	0.306
			BB50	0.838	0.84	0.841	0.714	0.323
			BB100	0.843	0.844	0.846	0.711	0.331
			BB200	0.845	0.846	0.847	0.711	0.341
			SMOTE	0.742	0.744	0.745	0.74	0.384
			AdaSyn	0.707	0.709	0.711	0.73	0.366
			Fair-SMOTE	-	0.66	-	0.59	0.38

Boosting Clinical Trials

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Progress in Biomedical Engineering

PERSPECTIVE • FREE ARTICLE

The potential synergies between synthetic data and *in silico* trials in relation to generating representative virtual population cohorts

Puja Myles^{3,1} , Johan Ordish¹ and Allan Tucker²

Published 24 January 2023 • © 2023 Crown copyright, Medicines and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency

[Progress in Biomedical Engineering, Volume 5, Number 1](#)

[Advances in *in silico* trials of medical products: evidence, methods and tools](#)

Citation Puja Myles *et al* 2023 *Prog. Biomed. Eng.* 5 013001

DOI 10.1088/2516-1091/acafbf

Article PDF

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+ Article and author information

Abstract

In silico trial methods promise to improve the path to market for both medicines and medical devices,

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Synthetic Data & Geolocation

Synthetic Data & Geolocation

- Useful to understand impact of geography on health
- Incorporating location info poses risks of identification
- Can we use other aggregated data to allocate synthetic data to regions?

AIM

CPRD COVID-19 symptoms and risk factors synthetic dataset

This synthetic dataset is based on anonymised real primary care patient data extracted from the [CPRD Aurum database](#). The dataset focuses on patients presenting to primary care with symptoms indicative of COVID-19 (confirmed/suspected COVID-19) and control patients with negative COVID-19 test results. The dataset includes data on sociodemographic and clinical risk factors.

The development of this dataset was funded by NHSX using the synthetic data generation and evaluation framework developed under a grant from the Regulators' Pioneer Fund launched by The Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy (BEIS) and managed by Innovate UK.

GOLD STANDARD

70K population

Publication, Part of [Quality and Outcomes Framework](#)

Quality and Outcomes Framework, 2020-21

Official statistics

Publication Date: 30 Sep 2021
Geographic: England
Coverage:
Geographical: GP practices, Dental practices, Pharmacies and clinics, Regions, Clinical Commissioning Groups,
Granularity: Country, Strategic Health Authorities, Primary Care Organisations, Clinical Commissioning Regions, Sustainability and Transformation Partnerships
Date Range: 01 Apr 2020 to 31 Mar 2021

AIM

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Date Range: 01 Apr 2020 to 31 Mar 2021

+5M population

Synthetic Data & Geolocation

- Can we create synthetic patients with location information based on GP profiles?

Real and Simulated health conditions percentage related to the region population

Synthetic Data & Drift

Synthetic Data & Drift

- Primary care data is updated in batches
- Regulating AI devices based on performance
- But as new data is generated these statistics may change
- How to deal with this “Drift”?

Drift: experimental protocol

1. Split the data in batches and generate s samples from the first batch. Then, fit s models and test them on subsequent batches computing a performance metric.

2. Define the control set (i.e., our baseline) and the next batch in time. Compare the metric distributions with the Wilcoxon Rank test to assess concept drift.

Drift: case studies

CVD dataset

COVID-19 dataset

Interaction between Drift and Bias

(a)

(b)

Protected attribute: *Ethnicity*. Results obtained on the original CVD dataset by evaluating the model's performance with recall metric on the whole population (a), *Black Caribbean* population group (b), and *Indian* group (c).

(c)

Interaction between Drift and Bias

(a)

(b)

Protected attribute: *Ethnicity*. Results obtained on BB200 dataset by evaluating the model's performance with recall metric on the whole population (a), *Black Caribbean* population group (b), and *Indian* group (c)

(c)

Press release

Transforming the regulation of software and artificial intelligence as a medical device

The Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) is updating regulations applying to software and artificial intelligence (AI) as a medical device.

RF Quarterly

Volume 1 • Number 2

Synthetic data and the innovation, assessment, and regulation of AI medical devices

Puja Myles, PhD, MPH

Johan Ordish, MA

Richard Branson, MSc, MA

Synthetic data are artificial data that mimic the properties of and relationships in real data. They show promise for facilitating data access, validation, and benchmarking, addressing missing data and under-sampling, sample boosting, and the creation of control arms in clinical trials. The UK Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) is using its current research into the development of high-fidelity synthetic data to develop its regulatory position on AI medical devices trained on synthetic data, and on synthetic data as a tool for the validation and benchmarking of AI medical devices.

Introduction

The predicted rise of artificial intelligence (AI) for health and social care implies that AI as a medical device (AIaMD) will become an ever more prominent subcategory of medical device.¹ It is therefore increasingly important that medical device regulations are fit for purpose for AI and that manufacturers understand as well as comply with their obligations, chief of which is to demonstrate a favourable benefit-risk ratio for their AIaMD.² Robust datasets are core to demonstrating the performance of AIaMD and are often the chief blocker to the development of such devices.³ It is incumbent on medical device regulators to ensure manufacturers have at their disposal the tools necessary to comply with these

obligations and provide wider support to encourage the development of such innovative devices. The development of synthetic datasets may well constitute such an assistive tool. This paper outlines efforts by the MHRA to research and develop synthetic data and consider their use in the context of wider reforms to ensure medical device regulation is fit for purpose for AI.

The synthetic data landscape

Recent years have witnessed a growing interest in synthetic data due to a number of factors, including potential ease of access in a world with stricter data governance regulations, protection of patient privacy, benchmarking and validation capabilities in the context of machine learning algorithms, and the ability to address limitations of real data, such as missing data, under-sampling, and small samples.⁴ More importantly, although the potential applications of synthetic data have been discussed for many years, it is only recently that methodologic advancements in synthetic data generation have been able to yield high-quality synthetic data.⁵

Defining synthetic data

Conceptually, synthetic data are artificial data that mimic the properties of and relationships in real data. The quality of synthetic data depends on the approach taken to synthetic data generation. The quality of

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Summary

- Synthetic data is useful in validating and improving models
- Classes of generative models offer promise
- But always a trade-off between utility and privacy:
 - Aggregated data vs personalised interventions
 - National or Regional Datasets / Models
 - Rare disease / Marginalising over many features

Summary

- Dealing with Bias is important
 - Not just to balance difficult datasets
 - Identify unwarranted links, semantics of latent variables
- Dealing with Drift is important
 - Data is often dynamic
 - Need to identify / handle changing populations

Further Work

- Other types of bias
 - Label inconsistencies
 - Identifying proxies for bias using Domain Adversarial Networks
- Combining graphical models with GANs using causal GANs
- Extending Bayesboost to multiple morbidities and multiple sensitive attributes
- Boosting / Informing future clinical trials
- Explore Fairness, Transparency and Explainability throughout

Thanks

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- Zhenchen Wang
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- Asal Khoshravi
- Dima Alattal

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Dealing with Bias

- Domain Adversarial Networks (Ganin et al., JMLR 2016)
 - Identify “sensitive” attributes
 - Build neural networks that are “agnostic” to these attributes when making decisions

- e.g. learning to recognise animals by ensuring background scenery does not influence the decisions